

PROFESSIONAL QUALITIES OF THE LEADER IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION MANAGEMENT

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Annotation: The study of issues of development of management competence of the head of preschool educational organization requires to refer to the methodology of management activity, to determine the scientific basis necessary for the research problem of interdisciplinary analysis. The management competencies of the head of the preschool educational organization are inextricably linked with the main categories of administration and management science. In this regard, the study of the essence of management competence, its uniqueness, structure requires the analysis of the scientific foundations of the theory and practice of management activity.

Key words: Management, leader, management, competence, director, document, knowledge, education.

Research on the formation of management competence of the head of a preschool educational organization is based not only on the selection of content, but also on the involvement of leaders in practice-oriented management activities, within the framework of which leaders directly mastered various management skills and methods of solving management tasks. Determining the organizational aspects of the management competence development process of the head of a preschool educational organization, we were based on the main rules of the competence approach, in particular:

- to strengthen the personal orientation of the management formation process, i.e. to create selection conditions that activate the educational process, relying on the

interests and needs of leaders; this means that the leader should search for himself, create his own knowledge;

- teaching to solve professional problems by developing new types and methods of activity. In this regard, it is important not only to acquaint leaders with the scientific foundations and various methods of performing management activities, but also to bring them into the situation of design, analysis, evaluation and self-evaluation;

- directing a person to self-development. The main requirement for us is to create conditions for leaders to demonstrate their independence and creativity in solving proposed management tasks, as well as to give them the opportunity to see their own growth and achievements.

It follows from the theoretical rules of the competence approach that the main part of teaching should be a practical task (situation), in the process of solving it, the development of methods of activity implementation, the formation of skills, and the experience of the head of preschool education organizations in management activities. should be. In order to ensure the effective solution of professional management tasks, the willingness to competently perform the management functions of a preschool educational organization, the experience of solving practical problems, which is an indicator of the formation of management skills, at the same time, the leaders are required to engage in real practical management activities to manage preschool educational organizations. readiness is taken into account. However, this activity can be specially modeled as a part of individual training sessions through the use of simulation forms: management practice, simulated practical management in the form of a game, etc.

These scientific positions envisage the organization of the process of development of leadership competence, the implementation of the goals, tasks, and methods of the management activities of the head of the preschool educational organization in his future professional activity. At the same time, in practically oriented activities, it is understood that the leader learns professional knowledge,

improves the quality of the educational process, and social modeling of management activities. The result is that practical activity is a personal experience, and in turn, the development of the professional competence of the leader in solving management problems is the basis. The most important thing is that the relations and supports that stimulate the activity of the educational process support personal equality in the aspect of management activity of leaders. In the process of formation of leadership competence, it is important to guide the activities of leaders in a practical way, to carry out experiments using educational methods (assistance, case study), game simulation (simulation, business, role-playing game).

Our goal is to provide listeners with in-depth knowledge of the social, psychological, specific aspects of management, initiative and leadership qualities, as well as the ability to think logically, make effective management decisions, on the basis of improving general professional preparation (as an example of management psychology). consists of forming skills and management values.

In the 1940s, 79 qualities of leadership were defined by E. Bern[32]. This list included such qualities as initiative, communication skills, sense of humor, self-confidence, quick and clear decision-making. But the error of this theory is that it could not explain how the above qualities are manifested and how they are formed. From this we can conclude that it is not easy to create a leadership model.

The human race requires him to follow the same role. This situation is especially evident in the conditions of eastern countries and our region. Sexual and social norms specific to men and women are clearly defined in this area. As long as this is the case, most of the behavior performed by a person is perceived under the influence of this sex role criterion. Now, regardless of a person's gender, we see great opportunities emerging in the career or career ladder.

In our country, a great way has been opened for women in the field of entrepreneurship and public administration. But, despite this, the word leader is often compared to the male gender, and for some reason, it does not go beyond education, health care, and public service as the areas managed by a female leader.

In fact, a woman's holding a management position in one or another field largely depends on the question of whether this field is suitable for women or for men. According to a number of studies, men often take the initiative in a mixed working group. According to the experience of researcher R. Stogdill [119], men can find a more acceptable way to solve a task within a group, and they strive for superiority in a mixed group. According to the scientist, this kind of behavior characteristic of men, to a large extent, comes from the norms and expectations of men's behavior established in society. The standards based on such installations have a great impact on the perception of the surrounding people.

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